

The Traces of Religious Education in the Poem “Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga” by Hartono “John Witir”

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ABSTRACT: This article examines the poem “Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga” by Hartono “John Witir” as a literary work that reflects spiritual and religious values, particularly in the context of awareness of the afterlife. This poem explicitly serves as an invitation for self-reflection on worldly arrogance that has the potential to distance individuals from God, as well as a warning about the dangers of pride that can cloud one’s conscience. This study aims to elucidate the religious educational ideology contained in the poem. Using a qualitative descriptive approach, the object of study is the poem “Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga” itself. The analysis was conducted by applying hermeneutic theory, utilising quotations from the poem that directly represent religious educational values. The data collection process involved three stages: collection, reduction, and presentation of data. Subsequently, the data were analysed descriptively to produce an accurate and comprehensive picture of the characteristics and interconnections of the elements under study. The findings of this study indicate that the poem “Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga” by Hartono “John Witir” contains dimensions of religious relationships that include interactions between humans and God, humans and their fellow humans, and humans and themselves. Of these three forms of religious relationships, the relationship between humans and God is the most dominant aspect in this poem.

Keywords: Poetry “Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga”, Religious Education, Hermeneutics

INTRODUCTION

Islamic education prioritises religious values and objectives as the core of its educational process. This ideology, as explained by Mustopa et al. (2021), is a collection of systematised concepts that serve as a basis for thinking and determining the direction of life. Conservative religious movements believe that education should be built on the foundation of religious values, particularly in terms of objectives and the types of knowledge taught. Methods such as mujahadah, riyadah, practical discipline, and the use of textual and rational evidence are often applied in teaching (Aisyah et al., 2024). The importance of comprehensively instilling a religious nationalist spirit in Indonesian society can be achieved both directly and indirectly, for example through mass media and literary works that contain such values (Mahmudi & Yunianta,

2022).

Poetry, as one form of literary work, is highly strategic in conveying Islamic values, especially Sufi poetry that addresses themes of divinity. Sufi poetry has a broad scope of religious teachings and has a significant impact on society through its educational and entertaining narrative and word choice. Through the reading of poetry, society can understand, be emotionally moved, and draw relevant life lessons (Sahli, 2016). Religious values greatly influence human behaviour and attitudes. Poetry, especially religious poetry or the works of Sufi poets, is often used as a medium for conveying messages, not only containing religious advice but also moral, national, struggle, social, cultural, environmental, and spiritual values.

Hartono 'John Witir' is one of the poets who addresses the theme of divinity. His poems, including those highlighting the dangers of arrogance that can blind one's conscience, depict the inner struggle between worldly desires and the divine call. He emphasises that true victory lies in surrendering oneself to God before death, not in worldly power or grandeur. The story of Pharaoh is even used as a historical analogy as a warning of the consequences of tyranny.

In a broader context, education encompasses vision, mission, objectives, curriculum, and learning strategies, all of which can be interpreted. As a text or discourse, education is suitable for hermeneutics, whether as a method, philosophy, or criticism. The diversity of Islamic educational institutions in Indonesia, such as pesantren, schools, and madrasahs, shows the close relationship between education and hermeneutics (Budianto & Fadholi, 2020). Currently, hermeneutics is one of the popular approaches in analysing poetry. This approach focuses on interpreting the meaning and message contained in literary works (poetry) without neglecting structuralist aspects, but rather going further to explore other elements (Dewi et al., 2022). Specifically, the poem "Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga" tells of the danger of arrogance that clouds the conscience, depicts the conflict between worldly desires and divine calls, and affirms <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15721616>

that true victory is the submission of the soul before death. The story of Pharaoh is again mentioned as a historical example of the impact of tyranny.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Religious Values

Although the term ‘religious’ is often associated with ‘religion,’ the two have different meanings. Ade Rufaida (2019) explains that religiosity is a set of values that reflect a sense of togetherness with something invisible, not merely an understanding of religion, but consistent practice in daily life. Heri Jauhari (2010) adds that the concept of religion is broader than religion. In Islamic theology, religious values can be explained through several aspects:

a) Faith (Tawhid): This refers to human belief in the existence, essence, and attributes of God, which is manifested in servitude. According to Heri Jauhari (2010), the religious aspect of tawhid includes faith in Allah, piety towards Him, and repentance.

b) Religious Aspect of Fiqh: Related to the rules and norms of life that originate from religious principles (Heri Jauhari, 2010). Jasser Audah defines fiqh as a school of thought that can be applied in life. Hafsa (2016) mentions examples of fiqh aspects such as halal, haram, makruh, sunat, and mubah.

c) Religious Aspect of Ethics: According to Islamic scholar Ibrahim Anis, ethics are the qualities formed within a person’s soul, prompting good or bad actions spontaneously without the need for deep consideration. Examples include patience, tawakal (trust in God), humility, honesty, sincerity, discipline, dzikrullah (remembering God), gratitude, and fulfilling one’s duties (Sahriansyah, 2014).

2. Poetry

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2.1. Definition of Poetry

According to Kinayati Djojuroto (2005), the term 'poetry' comes from the Greek word 'poesis,' which means 'creation.' In English, it is known as 'poem' or 'poetry,' with 'poet' referring to the poet and 'poem' to the verse or rhyme. Poetry is a form of literary art composed of carefully chosen words, arranged with rhythm, rhyme, and figurative language, and is dominant in expressing feelings, unlike prose, which focuses more on thoughts. Some other experts argue that poetry is an attempt to seek and describe 'the desired' or ideal ideas.

2.2. Structure of Poetry

Poetry has two main structures: physical and internal. Physical structure refers to visible linguistic elements, while inner structure relates to the meaning of the poem.

1. Physical Structure of Poetry

According to Titih Nuraini (2021), the physical structure of poetry is the visually apparent aspect. Kinayati Djojuroto (2005) outlines the elements that form the physical structure of poetry as follows:

- a) Diction: This is the foundation of poetry, involving the selection of words that match the feelings and mood. Poets carefully consider the primary meaning (denotation) and secondary meaning (connotation) to create associations. The process of selecting diction is very careful and systematic, often involving repetition until the most appropriate words for the mood of the poem are found.
- b) Style: Kinayati Djojuroto (2005) explains that style is used to create imaginative enjoyment, add meaning, increase the intensity of the poet's emotional conflict, and condense meaning. Style is generally divided into ornamentation (decoration) and symbolism.

c) Sound: The role of sound is crucial in determining the meaning of a poem when read. Discussions of sound in poetry include rhyme (similarity or repetition of sounds), rhythm (regular repetition of sounds forming waves between lines), and metre (variations in word or syllable stress).

2. The Inner Structure of Poetry

The inner structure of poetry is a unity of meaning consisting of the theme (main idea), feelings, tone, and message that the poet wants to convey (Kinayati Djojuroto, 2005). To understand it, readers must engage emotionally with the nuances of the poem in order to grasp the meaning conveyed. One way to engage is by understanding the codes within the poem, which, according to Teeuw (1984), include linguistic, literary, and cultural codes. Readers must be aware that the meaning of a poem requires interpretation, not direct comprehension. This can be achieved by interpreting linguistic contexts such as diexis, cohesion, and coherence. Kinayati Djojuroto (2005) details the elements of the inner structure of poetry as follows:

a) Theme: This is the main idea conveyed by the poet, often raising fundamental human issues such as love, fear, happiness, suffering, justice, truth, divinity, social criticism, and protest. Sayuti et al. state that the theme is the author's basic idea in creating poetry. For example, poetry about social processes and history raises themes related to reality and historical events. Hartoko adds that poetry with a theme of divinity usually describes the poet's dialogue with God or his personal reflections.

b) Tone: Often associated with mood. Tone reflects the poet's attitude towards the subject matter (feeling) and towards the reader (tone), while mood is the emotional state that arises from the expression of tone and the environment captured by the senses. Tone is related to the theme and the reader; for example, the tone can be sympathy, hatred, anticipation, or emotion. The

reader's appreciation of tone is very important in approaching the meaning intended by the poet. One way to interpret is to review the language used and determine the context of the poem based on the cohesion and coherence between sentences.

c) Feelings: Poetry expresses the poet's feelings completely, without reservation, such as joy, sadness, emotion, fear, curiosity, love, or resentment. Tarigan (1984) states that poets use all their linguistic abilities to reinforce this complete expression of feelings.

d) Message: Poetry contains a message, advice, or appeal from the poet to the reader. According to Sri Wahyuni (2018), a message is advice, a message, or a lesson conveyed by the poet either directly or indirectly through their work.

3. Hermeneutics

The term 'hermeneutics' became widely known in the 17th and 18th centuries, referring to a set of rules for accurately interpreting and understanding ancient texts, especially sacred texts and classical works. The word was adopted from the English hermeneutics, which comes from the Greek verb *hermeneuô*, meaning to interpret, explain, or translate (Bertens, 2002).

Hermeneutics can be defined in at least six forms:

a) Biblical Exegesis Theory: Originally and still often understood, hermeneutics refers to the principles of biblical interpretation.

b) General Philological Methodology: With the development of rationalism and classical philology in the 18th century, biblical hermeneutics was also influenced. This gave rise to the historical-critical method in theology, which claims that the methods of interpreting the Bible (grammatical and historical) can also be applied to other texts.

c) Linguistic Understanding: Thinkers such as Schleiermacher saw hermeneutics as the science <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15721616>

or art of understanding. This conception radically criticised the philological view that hermeneutics was merely a collection of rules. Schleiermacher sought to make it a systematic and coherent science, describing the conditions of understanding in every dialogue. The result was general hermeneutics, whose principles became the foundation for all types of text interpretation.

d) Methodological Foundations of the Humanities (Geisteswissenschaften): Wilhelm Dilthey regarded hermeneutics as the core discipline underlying all humanities, i.e., disciplines focused on understanding human art, action, and writing. Interpreting human expressions of life, whether in law, literature, or sacred texts, requires historical understanding.

e) Phenomenology of Existence and Existential Understanding: In this context, hermeneutics no longer refers to the science of text interpretation or the methodology of the humanities, but rather to a phenomenological explanation of human existence itself. Heidegger's analysis shows that understanding and interpretation are fundamental models of human existence. Thus, Heidegger's 'hermeneutics of Dasein,' particularly as an ontology of understanding, is also considered hermeneutics his research is hermeneutics both in terms of content and method.

f) System of Interpreting the Meaning of Myths and Symbols: Hermeneutics is also understood as a system used by humans to seek the hidden meaning behind myths and symbols.

METHOD

This study adopts a descriptive qualitative approach, applying Paul Ricoeur's hermeneutics theory to interpret religious values in poetry. Ricoeur's hermeneutics was chosen for its ability to deeply explore the direct and symbolic meanings of a text, enabling a rich analysis of symbols in historical and philosophical dimensions (Somadayo et al., 2022). The strength of Ricoeur's approach lies in its ability to analyse not only the internal structure of the text but also the interaction between the reader and the religious symbols contained within it.

The data analysis technique uses a descriptive analytical method, which aims to explain or describe the facts, characteristics, and relationships between the phenomena being studied in a sequential, factual, and actual manner (Hasibuan et al., 2020). The data analysis process began with data collection through listening to and recording the verses and lines of the poem “Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga” by Hartono “John Witir,” which contains religious values. Next, the data was reduced by grouping the verses and lines that were relevant to describing religiosity. The data analysis stage was conducted using Ricoeur’s hermeneutic approach, which consists of three phases: prefiguration to identify the initial understanding of the social context when the poem was written, configuration to construct the text structure and explore the symbolic meaning of phrases, and refiguration to relate the interpretation results to the relevant social-religious context at that time. Through this approach, it is hoped that a comprehensive understanding of religiosity in the poem will be obtained, both from the poet’s perspective and its relevance to contemporary readers.

FINDINGS

In poetry, religiosity is manifested through three interrelated types of relationships: between humans and God, between fellow humans, and between humans and themselves. The poem ‘Before the Soul Leaves the Body’ by Hartono ‘John Witir’ can be analysed to discover various meanings of religious education. The findings of religious education analysis in this poem, using Paul Ricoeur’s hermeneutics method, are presented as follows.

1. Religiousness between Humans and God

As creatures of Allah SWT, humans are obliged to obey all His commands and avoid His prohibitions, an action that demonstrates obedience to the Creator. This aspect of the relationship between humans and God is manifested in the following verses of the poem.

“Sadarlah wahai jiwa yang zolim”

“Kemenangan yang kau rasa sebenarnya adalah kekalahan”

“Surga yang kau rasa di dunia, sesungguhnya jalanmu ke neraka”

“Segeralah bersujud mohon ampunan-Nya”

“Sebelum nyawa terlepas dari raga”

In the first stanza, there is a religious value concerning the human-God relationship. The lines of the poem *“Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga”* powerfully depict the essential relationship between humans and God, highlighting the urgency of self-awareness and repentance. The call *“Sadarlah wahai jiwa yang zolim”* and the statement *“Kemenangan yang kau rasa sebenarnya adalah kekalahan”* are divine admonitions that invite reflection on wrongdoings and serve as a reminder of the ultimate judgment. The invitation *“Segeralah bersujud mohon ampunan-Nya”* and the warning *“Sebelum nyawa terlepas dari raga”* emphasize the importance of humility, confession of sins, and the urgency of returning to God before time runs out, underlining that true salvation lies in a vertical relationship with the Creator.

2. Relationship between Humans and Other Humans

Religiosity in the context of inter-human relationships or among individuals is manifested through how they interact and behave towards others. Such behaviors include doing good, showing interfaith tolerance, and demonstrating mutual help or care. This aspect can be observed in the first stanza of the poem as follows:

“Ketika tahta menguasai jiwa”

“Ketika mimpi tak beralas hati nurani”

“Tak peduli apa kata mereka”

“Bahkan Tuhan pun dianggap tiada”

The line *“Tak peduli apa kata mereka”* explicitly shows an attitude of extreme individualism and disregard for the opinions or suffering of others. This indicates a social indifference and egoism that arises from greed and ambition (*“tahta menguasai jiwa”*, *“mimpi tak beralas hati nurani”*). A person trapped in this condition tends to ignore norms, ethics, and the rights of others, even to the point of dismissing criticism or advice from their social environment. This attitude damages harmony in human relationships.

3. Relationship between Humans and Themselves

Religiosity in the dimension of the human relationship with oneself is manifested through actions, such

as the emergence of regret towards oneself or God. This internal phenomenon is a process experienced by a person, which then leads them to an awareness of God and obedience to His commands and prohibitions. This aspect can be observed in the first stanza of the poem, as will be explained below:

“Ketika tahta menguasai jiwa”

“Ketika mimpi tak beralas hati nurani”

These lines describe internal conflict and the human inner condition. *“Tahta menguasai jiwa”* indicates a loss of self-control, where ambition and material power have overridden reason and conscience. *“Mimpi tak beralas hati nurani”* suggests that life’s goals or desires are no longer based on morality and inner goodness, but merely on lust. This is a condition where a person’s self has been internally corrupted, losing their personal moral compass.

A religious relationship between humans and themselves is also found in the second stanza, as follows:

“Saat logika berpikir nafas tak berakhir”

“Saat jiwa merasa menang tak kan ada lawan”

“Tak ada rasa takut akan hari kemudian”

“Karena rasa itu t’lah tertutup bisikan syetan”

This stanza very strongly depicts the damaged relationship between humans and themselves, namely through arrogance, the illusion of immortality, and spiritual blindness. *“Logika berpikir nafas tak berakhir”* shows the delusion that life is eternal, ignoring the reality of death. *“Jiwa merasa menang tak kan ada lawan”* is a manifestation of arrogance and excessive feelings of superiority. The absence of *“rasa takut akan hari kemudian”* is an indication of neglecting one’s conscience and inner warnings about accountability in the afterlife. All of this is explained as a result of *“bisikan syetan”* (satanic whispers) that have closed the heart and reason, indicating an internal battle between good and evil within oneself.

A religious relationship between humans and themselves is also found in the third stanza, as follows:

“Sadarlah wahai jiwa yang zolim”

“Kemenangan yang kau rasa sebenarnya adalah kekalahan”

“Surga yang kau rasa di dunia, sesungguhnya jalanmu ke neraka”

This section is the peak of the depiction of the human relationship with oneself, namely in the form of a call for introspection and self-awareness. *“Sadarlah wahai jiwa yang zolim”* is a direct invitation to oneself (the soul) to realize the injustice that has been committed. The statements that *“kemenangan yang kau rasa sebenarnya adalah kekalahan”* and *“surga yang kau rasa di dunia, sesungguhnya jalanmu ke neraka”* constitute an internal realization that one’s perception of oneself has been wrong and will be detrimental in the future. This is a call to realign one’s heart and mind, perform self-correction, and return to the true nature.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Hermeneutics theory is a framework of knowledge that focuses on personal aspects and serves as a guide for understanding the reality around humans. Interpreting literary works through hermeneutics broadens our understanding of human behavior and creations. Hermeneutics can also be applied in education, especially in learning, where there is a correlation between classroom actions and the texts being studied (Sidik & Sulistyana, 2021). For example, understanding meaning in learning is similar to understanding meaning in a text (Firmanto & Anam, 2022). Religiosity, similar to individual character, is also reflected in the valuable world of education. Religious values are taught in educational institutions to foster discipline and religious obedience, so that the relationship between humans and their God does not experience a gap (Mulyono & Triana, 2022; Saputra et al., 2024).

After the process of data identification and analysis, several forms of religious relationships were found in the poem “Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga” by Hartono “John

Witir". These relationships include religiosity between humans and God, religiosity between fellow humans (or *hablumminannas*), and religiosity between humans and themselves. The religiosity depicted in this poem represents a person finding their true self and spiritual goodness, which encourages them to improve their relationship with God by obeying His commands and avoiding His prohibitions. This relationship with God that brings good impact to a person's life is often referred to as *hablumminallah*. Religiosity among fellow humans is manifested in the form of tolerance, love, and other good deeds. Meanwhile, the religious relationship between humans and themselves is expressed through the revelation of guilt, inner dialogue, and an attitude of seeking forgiveness from God (Somadayo et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the analysis conducted, it can be concluded that the poem "Sebelum Nyawa Terlepas Raga" by Hartono "John Witir" illustrates three forms of religiosity: between humans and God, between fellow humans, and between humans and themselves. Of these three relationships, religiosity between humans and God is the most dominant in this poem.

The religious education in the poem is clearly reflected through various symbols. The symbols "*tahta*" and "*mimpi tak beralas hati nurani*" represent worldly desires, while "*nafas tak berakhir*" symbolizes the illusion of eternity, and "*bisikan syetan*" depicts temptation. The concept of "*hari kemudian*" represents the afterlife. Furthermore, the phrases "*kemenangan yang kau rasa sebenarnya adalah kekalahan*" and "*surga yang kau rasa di dunia, sesungguhnya jalanmu ke neraka*" serve as paradoxical symbols of divine truth that teach about true value. The story of "*Firaun yang melegenda*" becomes a concrete symbol of the consequences of arrogance and tyranny. All these symbols synergize to convey didactic messages regarding self-awareness, repentance, and the importance of orienting oneself towards spiritual values. To achieve the objective of conveying the educational ideology in this poem, the research analyzes the value of religiosity education using hermeneutics theory to uncover

meaning based on personal human experience. This research is expected to enrich the understanding of the impact of the poem's religious values on education.

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